

POLICY BRIEF

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

THE EUROPE AND BRAZIL SUBMARINE CABLE INITIATIVE: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

AUTHOR: Danielle Jacon Ayres Pinto

POLICY STATEMENT

The virtual connection between Brazil and other countries worldwide was always made with submarine cables connected in the USA as a crossing point. To Brazil, that reality is a meaningful connection to improve its share communication with other actors, but, on the other side, it represents a Brazilian virtual system dependence on USA infrastructure and a threat about how safe and inviolable the information traffic would be. In that perspective, and after Snowden denounces, the Brazilian government of Dilma Rousseff started on 2014 a negotiation with Europe to build a high-performance submarine cable between the cities of Fortaleza, on the Brazil northeast, and Sines, on the south of Portugal. The main target with that project was to withdraw the Brazil submarine cable dependence on the USA and create an alternative way to share virtual information with other great international players – Europe, that had its leaders also spied on by NSA as Snowden sad. The submarine cable was launched last June 1st and now represents the most critical way to connect Brazil to the world.

BACKGROUND

Usually, when we think about virtual space or cyberspace, we do not realize how the information traffic has flowed worldwide. People often think that all kinds of information shared on the internet happened in an invisible space, a kind of cloud where data flows away. Nevertheless, that is wrong. Since the 19th century, the connection between different continents is made by cable on the sea. Submarine cables make telegraph communication, telephone communication, and the internet. Without that kind of infrastructure, it is almost impossible to connect all the world to the virtual space.

So, in a society even more integrated by technology, the international economy has become more dependent on improving its communication and logistics process. The consumers and part of the production chain are spread worldwide, and it is necessary to find a way to connect them to improve the economy, commerce, and production process⁽¹⁾.

On the other side, the submarine cable is not just used to flow private sector information; the State also has to use then to connect the bureaucratic spheres of government and share confidential information and data. So, almost 95% of voice and internet traffic produced by the State, Private Sector, individuals, Military, and other actors are made by submarine cables. That kind of data transfer is cheaper and faster than satellite way⁽²⁾.

In that scenario, submarine cable seems to be the most relevant virtual infrastructure that the State should concern in its strategic national demands. USA and China are the principal hubs to submarine cables worldwide, and we understand their importance. In 2019, more than 400⁽³⁾ cables crossing the sea and are then responsible for more than 15 million financial transactions a day that movement more than ten trillion US dollars a day⁽⁴⁾.

FINDINGS

The initiative of Brazil and Europe about the high-performance submarine cable is a public initiative but involves the technology company named EllaLink. The submarine cable has 6 thousand kilometers of extension and costs more than 170 million euros (most of that money invested by EllaLink), and the cable pass-through French Guiana, Cape Vert, Canarias Island, and Madeira Island.

What is the Brazilian plan for this cable? The purpose was to avoid the concentration of virtual communication service on the USA submarine cables in the begging. However, with the 5G technology, with all digitalization of things, and after the pandemic period who change the way everybody socializes in the virtual space, that new cable will gain another function.

The MCTI (Brazilian Ministry of Science, Technology, and Innovation) has announced on the submarine cable launched that for Brazil, the cable will increase the opportunity to improve the education and research process in all Latin America, especially using the public Brazilian digital platform named RNP (National Teaching and Research Network)⁽⁵⁾. The main objective is to interconnect European and Latin American academic institutions and promote more cultural and economic exchanges⁽⁶⁾.

On the other side, Brazil has a strategic objective for that submarine cable – make the city of Fortaleza a hub for submarine cables in Latin America, special in South America. Nowadays, Fortaleza receives nine international submarine cables and connects Brazil with the world⁽⁷⁾. With that infrastructure, Brazil, especially Fortaleza, will become the essential technological place for the companies that work inside the virtual space, and this reality represents a particular gain to Brazil and even the State of Ceará.

However, there are other improvements brought to the new submarine cable: 1) high capacity of connectivity because the data transmission speed is so fast; 2) low latency, due to the high speed to the data transmission will reduce the time it takes to leave an information one point to another, things like live streaming and games will happen faster and better; 3) Strategic Security, with a direct connection between Brazil and Europe the data are safer because do not need to pass through an intermediate country as the USA and that reduce risks of data espionage and interception.

On the other hand, the big challenge to the submarine cable is how Brazil, Europe, and the private company EllaLink will protect the submarine cable as strategic infrastructure. Who will be responsible for avoiding international espionage acts as happened in 2020 in Brazil with Russian Boat? That is the most important decision on this partner because, at the same time, it is a security matter, but also it is a defense matter, and the Brazilian Army and maybe NATO should be involved in this strategic planning of security.

CONCLUSIONS

The new submarine cable is a great technological innovation for Brazil and Europe, it can improve the economics transactions, the e-commerce, the cultural, educational and researchers exchanges between the two places, and, at the same time, can create a new way to connecting that places without an intermediary crossing point like US was. These opportunities represent a great scenario in the future to promote Brazil as a most important technological hub on the Latin America. But, at the other side, the big challenge for both Brazil and Europe are linked with how they think the process of critical infrastructure security to protect that submarine cable and how they included the private company EllaLink in this question. It is a problem because the cable protection is not a only cybersecurity problem, but also a cyber defense problem that should include the army and national security forces in the submarine cable security strategic plan.

SUGGESTIONS

Briefly, we now suggest some measures to improve the functions and protection of submarine cable:

- 1) Brazil needs to include the Public Universities in the creation of strategic plan to submarine cable academic and research exchanges. The Bolsonaro's government need to support more the Ministry of Education and to value more the science;
- 2) The Brazilian Strategic Plan to cybersecurity and cyber defense of critical infrastructure should be clearer in terms of who has responsibility to what. How army, government and private sector will interact on this situation should be a collective decision that involve the civil society too;
- 3) The Brazil cyber defense strategic plan needs to receive more budget to invest in preventive actions to protect submarine cables and should centralize that responsibility on the Brazil Navy hands;
- 4) Brazil and Europe should improve the dialogue between Brazil Army and NATO to think measures to protect that submarine cable and to avoid acts of espionage, sabotage and information interception.

REFERENCES

- (01) CLARK, Bryan. Undersea cables and the future of submarine competition. Bulletin of Atomic Scientists, v.72, n.4, p.234-237, 2016.
- (02) VICHÍ, L. P., AYRES PINTO, D.J.; SÁ, A.L.N. A defesa da infraestrutura de cabos submarinos: por uma interface entre a defesa cibernética e a segurança marítima no Brasil. Revista da Escola de Guerra Naval, v.26, n.2, p.326-346, 2020.
- (03) TELEGEOGRAPHY. Submarine Cable Frequently Asked Questions. Available in: <https://www2.telegeography.com/submarine-cable-faqs-frequently-asked-questions>
- (04) SUNAK, Rishi. Undersea Cables: indispensable, insecure. Policy Exchange. London: 2017.
- (05) BRAZIL, Official site of Brazil Government. Available in: <https://www.gov.br/pt-br/noticias/transito-e-transportes/2021/06/cabo-submarino-de-fibra-optica-brasil-europa-e-inaugurado-em-portugal>
- (06) EUROPEAN COMMISSION. Official site of European Commission. Available in: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/bella-new-digital-data-highway-between-europe-and-latin-america>
- (07) SUBMARINE CABLE MAP. Page of Fortaleza City cable map. Available in: <https://www.submarinemap.com/#/landing-point/fortaleza-brazil>